

Analysis of Soil Physicochemical Properties in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State, Nigeria

Nasiru H.B.¹, Ahmad R.S.¹, Augie, M.A.¹, Hamisu, I.¹ and Bello, I.M.²

¹Department of Soil Science, Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology, Aliero, Nigeria

²Department of Crop Science, Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology, Aliero, Nigeria

*Correspondence: nasiruhussainibk@gmail.com; +2348039365603

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Abstract

Agricultural productivity in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State, northwestern Nigeria, is under considerable strain due to declining soil fertility, inadequate soil management practices, and environmental degradation. Field experiment was conducted at Birnin Kebbi Local Government Area of Kebbi State to analyze the soil productivity indices for sustainable crop production in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State. Soil samples were collected from two soil strata. From each stratum, two composite samples were obtained; three borings were made using systematic random sampling, at the depth of 0-30 cm, 30-60cm and 60-90cm giving a total of six composite soil samples. The soil samples were analyzed in the laboratory using standard analytical techniques. Total Nitrogen (N), available Phosphorus(P), Potassium (K), pH, Moisture content (MC) and Electrical conductivity (EC) were determined and the data was analyzed using ANOVA where treatments show significant differences DMRT was used for mean separation. It was found that Soil NPK was high 30-60cm at sampling depth(1.1%, 8.0mg/kg⁻¹, 0.6cmol/kg⁻¹) in low land but found high at 0-30cm sampling depth (0.4% and 0.3cmol/kg⁻¹) in upland except P which was found high (0.8mg/kg⁻¹) in 60-90cm sampling depth. EC recorded highest mean value at 60-90cm sampling depth, while other parameters tested showed no significant differences. The research concluded that soil fertility is dynamics in Birnin Kebbi and is largely controlled by topography, drainage, and depth, underscoring the need for site-specific soil fertility management practices. Fertility management in uplands should emphasize organic matter addition and nitrogen supplementation at the surface layer to sustain crop productivity.

Keywords: Nitrogen, Potassium, Soil fertility, Soil strata and Topography

1.0 Introduction

Agricultural productivity in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State, Northwestern Nigeria, is under considerable strain due to declining soil fertility, inadequate soil management practices, and environmental degradation. Soil properties such as low organic carbon, poor nutrient availability (particularly nitrogen and phosphorus), unfavorable soil texture, and suboptimal soil structure limit crop yields and threaten long-term sustainability^[1]. Soil erosion, overgrazing, deforestation, and irregular application of fertilizers exacerbate this decline, leading to productivity losses that disproportionately affect smallholder farmers^[2].

Despite numerous studies on soil fertility status in Kebbi State, including investigations into Fadama lands (e.g. in Birnin Kebbi) where sandy loam textures and low nutrient concentrations have been documented^[3], and soil fertility mapping across Savanna zones^[2], there is a critical gap. Specifically, comprehensive assessment and quantification of soil productivity indices, which integrate multiple soil physical, chemical, and biological indicators to guide sustainable crop production in the Sudan Savanna of Kebbi are lacking. Without these indices, it is difficult to identify priority areas for intervention, optimize input use, or monitor soil quality changes over time. Therefore, this study aims to analyse soil productivity indices in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State with the objective of evaluating key

soil physical and chemical indicators that determine crop productivity.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Study Area

Kebbi State is situated in the extreme northwestern part of Nigeria, positioned between latitudes 10⁰ and 13⁰N and longitudes 30⁰30' and 6⁰E. Covering a total landmass of approximately 37,699 square kilometers, about 36.46% of this area is comprised of farmland, highlighting its agricultural significance. The state's diverse landscapes include plains, hills, and river valleys, contributing to its rich agricultural potential.

2.1.1 Climate of the study area

Like other Nigerian states, Kebbi State is characterized with the tropical weather conditions of coldness, wetness and harmattan. Sudan savanna of Kebbi State has overall averages of yearly and monthly total rainfall of 787.53±24.03 mm^[4]. The winds are predominantly NE and SW due to the passage of the inter-tropical convergence zone. Which are also the main procedures of rainfall? From November to February, the North-easterlies dominate and then from May to August, the south westerly dominates^[5].

The rainy season in the state is between mid-May and mid-September, while the dry season constitutes a period of seven months. The temperature of Sudan Savanna of Kebbi state has an annual variation between 65⁰F and 104⁰F^[6]. Average maximum temperature ranges, over a rainy season of 120 days a large water deficit occurs due to high potentials evaporation level throughout the year. The cloud of Kebbi state is clearer around November to March of the succeeding month, while the state is usually cloudy between March and November at 68% annually. There is a relatively high humidity between seven months, April and November of every year, with November to July being the windiest^[7].

2.1.2 Geology and Soil Topography of the study area

The region is situated on a rock formation the rock type is sedimentary consisting of Shales, limestone, the soil conditions is that of a sandy large textures which is freely drained. The geology of Kebbi State is characterized by thick and vast sequences of

sedimentary deposits of the Sokoto Rima-basin, which underline about 50% of the area. The rest being underlain by Precambrian Basement complex rocks. The state is within the tropical West Sudan in savanna Eco region. Important geographic features of Kebbi state include the Sokoto River, which flows through Kebbi into the River Niger, which continues south before reaching the Kainji Lake, half of which is in Kebbi^[4]. The predominant soil type in Kebbi State, however, is the ferruginous tropical soils. Their main features include a sandy surface horizon underlain by weakly developed clayey, mottled and sometimes concreting subsoil. Although, they are generally considered to be high in natural quality, they are very sensitive to erosion because once the vegetation cover is removed, the sandy topsoil are easily washed away by rain water and wind. The soil show low water holding capacity and are therefore susceptible to drought. Another type of soil that occurs in the state is the alluvial or fadama soil mostly found in Rima and Niger River Valleys. This soil is suitable for crop production. Farming in Kebbi State indeed depends to some extent on the fadama land that are sometimes several kilometres in width^[4].

According to^[8], the State has the following soil types: sandy soils found in the upland locations of the North, Northwest, and Central parts of the State. Ferruginous tropical soils in the south eastern parts, lateritic soils found throughout the State, black cotton soil in the south eastern and southern parts, and hydro orphic soils in the floodplains of the major rivers and enclosed depressions (Fadama areas). According to^[3], the soil of the Sudan Savanna in Kebbi State is sandy loam, which may explain why upland rice is grown in these areas. The soil can be considered medium in fertility, therefore, appropriate management practices such as the addition of organic matter, crop rotation, fallow periods, fertilizer application, and the cultivation of leguminous crops should be implemented for sustainable agricultural production.

2.1.3 Vegetation of the study area

The vegetation of the upland area is Sudan Savannah, with Shrub savannah of acacia trees and Shrubs with grasses mainly prophetic in nature, this vegetation rapidly returns when previously cultivated and is left fallow. However, is has little potential as range land fodder without pasture

improvement or as a firewood reserved due to sparseness of woody vegetation of sufficient girth. In the Fadama area, little natural vegetation exists due to continuous farming practices that which does exist in mainly grasses. A few palm trees producing coconuts are cultivated in occasional rows in the Sokoto Rima Fadama. In the Shella Fadama orchard cultivation are practical utilizing shallow wells for sources of irrigation water and producing Guava, Mango, Orange and some paw-paw^[8].

The natural vegetation in Kebbi State follows the rainfall pattern and other climatic elements. ^[9]reported that the vegetation of the State is broadly classified as Savanna and can be divided into three categories: Northern Guinea which occupies south-eastern parts of the State, Sudan Savanna which is found in the middle and the Sahel which is found in the extreme northern part of the State where sparse trees and shrubs of different kinds exist. The vegetation types could be related to evergreen forest, short medium forest (scattered clustered), dwarf vegetation (scattered isolated), grass vegetation, thick vegetation, stony-grass vegetation (scattered sparse) and short-length vegetation^[9].

3.1.4 People and Socio Economic Activities of the study area

Kebbi State has a total population of 3,238,628 as per 2006 National census comprises of 21 Local Government Areas and 4 Emirates Councils each under a first class Emir. They are Gwandu (with headquarters at BirninKebbi), Argungu, Yauri and Zuru. Emir of Gwandu is the Chairman of Kebbi State Council of Chiefs. Of the total population, however, males account for 1,617, 498 or 49.9% while the females are 1,621,130 or 50%^[9]. These are Hausa All over the state but dominant in areas like Birnin Kebbi, Argungu, Jega, Koko, Gwandu, Maiyama, Arewa and Augie Local Government Areas; Dakarkari (Lalna) Zuru, Danko-Wasagu and Sakaba Local Government Areas; Kambari Yauri, Ngaski, Danko-Wasagu and Sakaba Local Government Areas; Zabarmawa Dandi, Argungu, Bagudo and Birnin Kebbi Local Government Areas.^[10]

Agriculture is the major source of livelihood in the area. According to survey, Agricultural practices around the region vary according to topography. The Fadama area of the Sokoto Rima valley is dominated by flooding rice cultivation, here the

seed are planted at the end of the dry season and established itself before the annual flood arrives, which then support the rice in to maturity^[11]. On the higher parts of the Fadama which are not flooded of deeply or for such a longtime, vegetables are growing garden plots. Another area of Fadama exists to the southeast of the region along the shallow river although not as extensive as the Sokoto Rima Fadama and Flooding for a shorter time. The shallow river Fadama provides another important area of higher value agricultural soil. Here is group in the retreating flood quarters as well as other gain crops. Also there has been a recent development in tree cropping with a government as well as several private orchards being developed and extended using manual irrigations from shallow well. Upland agriculture is dependent on rainfall. The crops grown include sorghum cowpeas a millet and beans with some groundnut^[11].

Over eighty percent (80%) of people living in Kebbi state are peasant farmers. The state is blessed with tremendous livestock resources and potentials for meat/milk production, and draught-oxen for farm traction. Every household, in almost all the communities across the state, keeps one form of animal or the other, as an economic investment or as pet^[11].Kebbi state has an estimated livestock population of about 1.8million cattle, 2.2 million sheep, 2.8million goats, 50,000 camels, 200,000 donkeys, 20,000 horses and a large number of back yard scavenging poultry. These figures are mainly for the tradition livestock sub sector^[11].

The fisheries sub-sector contributes significantly to the Kebbi state economy, as it is estimated to provide employment to over 100,000 in the areas of artisanal fishing, processing and marketing.^[13]About 150km of the River Niger traverses Kebbi State, with an estimated surface area of 87,500 ha. In addition 50,000 ha of the Kainji lake (representing over half of its area) is in Kebbi State. The Sokoto Rima River also flows through the state to form an extensive flood plain of about 525,000 ha between Argungu and Suru Local Government areas, with about 142,000 ha remaining as dry season pool of stagnant water after the flood^[12].

Fishing in the region is in a medium scale and is of basic economic importance in the region. It is carried out manually in the river Sokoto, river Zamfara and streams within the region using

butterfly nets. Fish production in the state estimated at about 90,00mt making the state second in terms of fresh water fisheries resource in Nigeria. Fishing activity in the state is all year round, and peaks in

the dry season (October-April). Women are mainly involved in the processing aspect of the fishing industry^[12].

Figures 1,2, and 3:Maps of the Study Area

2.2 Method of Sampling

This study employed the use of two sample points. One from the up land and one from the low land as shown on the Table 1 below.

Table1: Soil Samples Collection Points

S/NO	L.G	Sample Point1	Sample Point2
1	Birnin Kebbi	Marafa	Kardi /Yamama

Source: Field Survey, 2024

2.3 Soil Samples collection

Soil samples were collected at different depth of 0-30cm, 30-60cm and 60-90cm in both upland and lowland locations using soil Auger. The samples were randomly collected and the subsamples were composited, prepared using pestle and moter, parked, labeled and transported to the laboratory for analysis. The analytical results from composite samples collected provided the average values for the sampled areas.

2.4 Analytical Procedures

The processed soil samples were analyzed for various physicochemical properties following the procedures as described by^[13]. Soil pH was measured in a 1:2 soil water suspension using a pH meter, Total Nitrogen was measured using the macro kjeldahl digestion method. Available phosphorous was obtained by the Bray-1 method (0.025NHCl+0.03N NH₄F) as Moisture content (MC) was determined using core sampling method. Electrical conductivity (EC) was determined in a 1:2 soil to water suspension at 25⁰C using a conductivity meter. The results were multiplied by a

conversion factor of 2.063 to obtain the saturation extract. Soil Temperature was determined using thermometer.

2.5 Data Analysis

Data generated from the research was analyzed using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) where treatments show significant differences at 5% level Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used for mean separation

3.0 Result

Table 2 shows the results of lowland composite soil samples at Birnin-kebbi local government area. The result indicated no significant difference at 5% level among the treatment mean on pH and Temperature but significance differences was detected on N, where 30-60cm sampling point recorded the highest mean value, which was statistically difference at 5% level with the rest of sampling point which recorded statistically the same. On the other hand, significant difference was also detected on MC and EC, in which 60-90cm sampling point recorded the highest mean value which differ with the rest of sampling point (0-30cm and 60-90cm).

Table 2: Lowland Soil Characteristics of Birnin Kebbi Local Government Area

Sampling Depth	N(%)	P(mg/kg ⁻¹)	K(cmol/kg ⁻¹)	pH	Temp(0 ^c)	MC(%)	EC(dSm ⁻¹)
0–30cm	0.8 ^b	5.0 ^b	0.3 ^b	8.0	30.0	46.0 ^c	0.2 ^c
30–60cm	1.1 ^a	8.0 ^a	0.6 ^a	7.5	30.0	52.0 ^b	0.2 ^b
60-90cm	0.9 ^b	6.0 ^b	0.5 ^b	7.0	28.0	81.0 ^a	0.3 ^a
SE±	0.11	1.02	0.31	1.17	2.38	1.06	0.03

Means followed with different letters (a,b,c) within the column are statistically differed at (0.05%) level of probability. N= Nitrogen, P=Phosphorus, MC=Moisture content and EC= Electrical conductivity.

Table 3 indicated the results of upland composite soil samples at Birnin kebbi local government area. The result showed no significant difference among the treatments on pH, Temperature and Moisture content (MC) across the sampling points. Significant differences were observed on the other variables tested. 0-30cm sampling point recorded the highest mean value of N which statistically

differ with 30-60cm and 60-90 sampling point that recorded statistically the same. Similar trend was observed with K but slightly different in which 60-90cm point recorded the least mean value. On P and EC, 60-90cm sampling point recorded the highest mean value that differ with the rest of sampling points.

Table 3: Upland Soil Characteristics of Birnin Kebbi Local Government Area

Sampling Depth	N(%)	P(mg/kg ⁻¹)	K(cmol/kg ⁻¹)	pH	Temp(0 ^C)	MC(%)	EC(dSm ⁻¹)
0–30cm	0.4 ^a	0.6 ^b	0.3 ^a	7.5	30	20	0.10 ^b
30–60cm	0.3 ^b	0.6 ^b	0.2 ^b	7.0	28	21	0.11 ^b
60-90cm	0.3 ^b	0.8 ^a	0.1 ^c	6.5	27	23	0.16 ^a
SE±	0.02	0.04	0.01	1.32	4.06	3.08	0.02

Means followed with different letters (a,b,c) within the column are statistically differed at (0.05%) level of probability. N= Nitrogen, P=Phosphorus, MC=Moisture content and EC= Electrical conductivity.

3.0 Discussion

Nitrogen content showed distinct depth-related differences. In the upland soils, nitrogen was highest at the 0–30 cm depth and decreased significantly with depth, which is consistent with the observations of [14] in Umudike, Abia State, who reported that nitrogen tends to decline with soil depth due to the higher organic matter concentration at the surface. A similar trend was reported by [15] along a catena in Kwambai, Taraba State, where upland soils exhibited surface enrichment of nitrogen. However, in the lowland soils of Birnin Kebbi, nitrogen peaked at the 30–60cm depth, which contrasts with the more common pattern of surface dominance. This unusual distribution could be attributed to leaching and subsequent accumulation of nitrogen in the subsoil. Similar result was also been reported by [15].

Phosphorus availability followed a different pattern. In the upland soils, phosphorus concentration was significantly higher at the 60–90 cm depth. This result differs from the findings of [16], who reported that phosphorus is generally concentrated in the topsoil due to litter deposition and fertilizer application, with limited mobility in deeper layers. The deeper accumulation of phosphorus in Birnin Kebbi upland soils may therefore be linked to soil mineralogy, parent material influence, or past management practices that favored downward movement of soluble forms of phosphorus. This result is in agreement with the findings of [16] who reported the movement of phosphorus downward is as a result of management practices.

Potassium showed significant variation across depths in both soil types. In upland soils, potassium

was highest at the surface and declined with depth, a pattern consistent with the findings of [16], who also observed surface enrichment of potassium linked to organic matter turnover and root cycling. In contrast, the lowland soils recorded the highest potassium concentration at 30–60 cm, which may be explained by redistribution through leaching or deposition in finer-textured layers.

Moisture Content and electrical conductivity also showed significant trends. In the lowland soils, both variables were highest at the 60–90 cm depth, whereas no significant depth-related differences were observed in upland soils. These results agree with those of [17] who reported increasing concentrations of magnesium in lowland subsoils, likely due to leaching and accumulation processes. The elevated electrical conductivity at deeper layers suggests some level of salt accumulation, which is characteristic of poorly drained or waterlogged environments, although the values obtained remain within non-saline limits for crop production. This result differ with the finding of [18] who reported salt accumulation at the surface of the soil.

Soil pH and temperature did not differ significantly across depths in either soil type. The soils were slightly alkaline in the lowlands (pH 7.0–8.0) and near neutral to slightly acidic in the uplands (pH 6.5–7.5). This stability across depths is in line with the findings of [6], who noted minimal variation in soil pH along toposequences in the humid tropics.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study on soil physicochemical parameters of Birnin Kebbi area revealed significant differences in nutrient distribution between lowland and upland

soils across different depths. Nitrogen and potassium were concentrated at the surface in upland soils but shifted to subsoil layers in lowland soils. These findings indicate that soil fertility dynamics in Birnin Kebbi are largely controlled by topography, drainage, and depth, underscoring the need for site specific soil fertility management practices. It's also indicated that soil of the study area require nutrients addition to meet the demand of the Agricultural activities taking place in the study area.

1. **Fertility management in uplands** should emphasize organic matter addition and nitrogen supplementation at the surface layer to sustain crop productivity.
2. **Lowland soils** require careful management of subsoil nutrients through deep incorporation of organic amendments and controlling drainage to improve nutrient availability and minimize nutrient leaching.
3. **Further research** on the influence of soil mineralogy, hydrology, and land use changes on the soil physicochemical parameters across depths should be conducted.

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7.0 Conflict of Interest

This work is a collaboration of all the authors. All Authors read and approved the final manuscript. They declare that they have no competing interests.

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